

Ethyl orange, another indicator recommended for this titration, has the advantage of being used in a high acid medium without the requirement of a catalyst; evidently vanadium(IV)-cerium(IV) reaction must be fast even under these titration conditions.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance to one of us (M.S.J.) from C.S.I.R., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Zinc

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Manuscript received 3 September 1983, accepted 27 February 1984

LITERATURE indicates that a large number of reagents have been utilized for the spectrophotometric determination of zinc, and several metal ions interfere in the determination¹⁻¹³. Hydroxamic acids have proved to be potential analytical reagents in inorganic and organic analysis¹⁴⁻²⁰. These acids are capable of forming strong and stable 5-membered ring complexes with several metal ions²¹. So far, few data are available for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of zinc utilizing the hydroxamic acids¹⁶.

In the present investigation a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of zinc is described.

Experimental

The spectral measurements were made on Carl Zeiss Speckol spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched cells. pH measurements were made with Systronics digital pH meter, Model 335 equipped with glass and calomel electrodes.

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck, G. R. grade unless otherwise stated.

N-m-Cl-Phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid (N-m-Cl-PPHA) was synthesized by literature method²² and a 0.1% solution was prepared in chloroform.

A 0.1% solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) was prepared in chloroform. A $2.3 \times 10^{-4} M$ zinc solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of zinc sulphate in double distilled water and the zinc content was determined titrimetrically²³.

Procedure : The pH of 2.0 ml zinc solution ($2.3 \times 10^{-4} M$) was adjusted to 8.0 with 0.1 M NH_4OH and 0.1 M NH_4Cl . To this was added 10 ml 0.1% reagent solution, and the contents were shaken vigorously for ~12 min. The phases were allowed to separate and the colourless organic layer extract was separated. The extraction was repeated with 5 ml reagent solution to ensure the complete extraction of zinc. Then 1.0 ml 0.1% PAN solution was added to the combined extract and the volume was made upto 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the dark pink coloured Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN complex was measured at 555 nm against a reagent blank, prepared in the same manner.

Results and Discussion

In the present method zinc is first extracted with hydroxamic acid followed by the addition of PAN to the extract. The dark pink coloured mixed complex of Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN shows a maximum absorption at 555 nm.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH on the extraction of zinc with N-m-Cl-PPHA was studied in the pH range 1-10.5. It was observed that the extraction commenced after pH 5.0 and was maximum at pH 7.5-10.0 (Table 1). At pH > 10 the extraction decreases. pH 8.0 was chosen for the extraction purposes.

Effect of reagent concentration : A 0.1% solution of N-m-Cl-PPHA is sufficient for complete extraction of zinc.

NOTES

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON THE EXTRACTION OF ZINC WITH N-m-Cl-PPHA

Zn : 1.21 ppm ; solvent : chloroform ; N-m-Cl-PPHA : 0.1% (10 ml) ; PAN : 0.1% (1 ml) ; Colour : dark pink ; λ_{max} : 555 nm.

pH	% E	Molar absorptivity l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1	*	*
3	*	*
5	23	7.7 × 10 ³
6	23	7.7 × 10 ³
7.0	38	1.2 × 10 ⁴
7.5	100	3.3 × 10 ⁴
8.0	100	3.3 × 10 ⁴
8.5	100	3.3 × 10 ⁴
9.0	100	3.3 × 10 ⁴
10.0	100	3.3 × 10 ⁴
10.5	40	1.3 × 10 ⁴

* No extraction.

Effect of PAN concentration : Various amounts of the PAN solution in chloroform were added to the colourless Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA complex. It was observed that 1 ml 0.1% solution was sufficient for complete colour development.

Absorption spectra : The Zn-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN complex shows a sharp absorption peak at 555 nm. Hence all measurements were made at this wavelength.

Effect of shaking time, stability and recovery : Shaking time of 10-12 min was sufficient for the complete extraction of Zn. The complex remains stable for 5-6 h and the extraction is quantitative.

Beer's law : The calibration curve for zinc was obtained under the optimum conditions. Beer's law is obeyed within the range of 0-2.71 ppm of Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN mixed complex at 555 nm. The molar absorptivity is 3.26 × 10⁴ l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Stoichiometry of the Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA complex : The stoichiometry of the Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA complex was determined by the molar ratio method^{2,4} following the above procedure. The PAN concentration was kept constant during all the determinations.

Fig. 1. Plot of distribution constant of metal D_m against $-\log[\text{ligand}]$ in chloroform.

It was found that the stoichiometry of Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA complex was 1 : 2 (Fig. 1).

Effect of diverse ions : Zinc was extracted in the presence of several other ions in order to judge the sensitivity and utility of the method. Most of the common metal ions associated with zinc do not interfere in the extraction of Zn (Table 2) except Hg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺. The interferences of Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ was eliminated by masking them with KI, while Mn²⁺ was masked with NaF.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF ZINC

Zinc : 1.21 ppm ; solvent : chloroform ; N-m-Cl-PPHA : 0.1% (10 ml) ; PAN : 0.1% (1 ml) ; pH : 8.0. Colour : dark pink ; λ_{max} : 555 nm ; Absorbance : 0.62.

Ions	Added as	mg	Absorbance
Be ²⁺	BeSO ₄	20	0.62
Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄	40	0.62
Ca ²⁺	CaCl ₂	40	0.62
Sr ²⁺	SrCl ₂	40	0.62
Ba ²⁺	BaCl ₂	40	0.62
La ³⁺	LaNO ₃	60	0.62
Ti ⁴⁺	TiCl ₄	40	0.62
Zr ⁴⁺	Zr(NO ₃) ₄ ·5H ₂ O	50	0.62
V ⁵⁺	NH ₄ VO ₃	60	0.62
Nb ⁵⁺	Nb ₂ O ₅	40	0.62
Ta ⁵⁺	Ta ₂ O ₅	40	0.62
Mo ⁶⁺	NH ₄ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	60	0.61
Fe ³⁺	Fe(SO ₄) ₂ (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ ·24H ₂ O	60	0.61
Co	CoCl ₂	40	0.62
Ni ²⁺	NiCl ₂ ·7H ₂ O	60	0.62
Cu ²⁺	CuSO ₄	60	0.61
Mn ²⁺	MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O**	30	0.62
Hg ²⁺	HgCl ₂ *	30	0.62
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ *	30	0.62
Cd ²⁺	3CdSO ₄ ·8H ₂ O*	30	0.62
Sn ²⁺	SnCl ₂	40	0.63
Al ³⁺	AlCl ₃ ·7H ₂ O	40	0.62
As ³⁺	As ₂ O ₃	50	0.62
Bi ³⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	60	0.62
Sb ³⁺	KSbOC ₂ H ₄ O ₆ ·7H ₂ O	40	0.62
Ce ⁴⁺	Ce(SO ₄) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	50	0.62

* Masked with KI. ** Masked with NaF.

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0.025M solution was prepared by dissolving DIH in anhydrous glacial acetic acid (9.5g dm⁻³) and kept in an amber coloured bottle. The solution was standardised daily by the usual iodometric method². Standard solutions of the reductants were prepared in appropriate solvents as described earlier^{6,9} and were checked by standard methods^{10,11}.

For potentiometric titrations the apparatus and electrode assemblies were as described earlier⁶. The usual procedures for the potentiometric, direct visual and excess back titrations were used.

Results and Discussion

Typical results of the titrations are presented in Table 1. The reduction half reaction of DIH is represented by the equation

where R=C₆H₆O₂. The product was found to be the hydantoin. The conditional redox potential of DIH in glacial acetic acid at 29° was +1.07 V.

Diiodohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant for Use in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 2 April 1983, revised 13 February 1984, accepted 26 May 1984

IN continuation of our work for the development of new redox titrants¹⁻⁶, we are now introducing diiodohydantoin, 1,3-diiodo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (DIH), for the use as an oxidimetric titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium. Direct potentiometric titrations are developed using DIH as the titrant for the determination of arsenic(III), antimony(III), tin(II), ferrocyanide, thiocyanate, sulphite, ascorbic acid, hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, hydroquinone, Reinecke's salt, mercury(II)-tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II) and mercury(II)-tetrathio-cyanato zincate(II). Direct visual titrations are developed for ascorbic acid, hydrazine, semicarbazide and Reinecke's salt. Direct titrations are unsuccessful for mercury(I), isonicotinic acid hydrazide, thiosemicarbazide, thiourea, phenol and aniline, for which excess back titrations are developed using DIH as the titrant.

Experimental

DIH was prepared by the iodination of 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as per the reported method⁷. It is sparingly soluble in water, but is fairly so in glacial acetic acid (19.8 g/kg at 29°). Approximately

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATIONS WITH DIODOHYDANTOIN

Reductant	Titrimetric method	Range of reductant taken m mol	Standard deviation* μ mol	Maximum error %
As ³⁺	b	0.05–0.17	0.30	0.47
Sb ³⁺	b	0.13–0.41	0.16	0.30
Sn ²⁺	b	0.11–0.21	0.20	0.36
Ferrocyanide	b	0.20–0.61	0.66	0.45
Thiocyanate	b	0.25–0.77	0.12	0.40
Sulphite	b	0.55–1.10	0.10	0.44
Ascorbic acid	a	0.39–0.86	2.40	0.40
	b	0.16–0.31	0.20	0.39
Hydrazine	a	0.24–0.74	2.90	0.36
	b	0.09–0.20	0.05	0.48
Phenylhydrazine	b	0.07–0.12	0.30	0.45
Semicarbazide	a	0.14–0.28	2.70	0.40
	b	0.05–0.09	0.18	0.40
Hydroquinone	b	0.16–0.27	0.20	0.40
Reinecke's salt	a	0.03–0.08	3.10	0.40
	b	0.01–0.02	0.02	0.40
Hg[Co(SCN) ₄]	b	0.004–0.015	0.04	0.41
Hg[Zn(SCN) ₄]	b	0.005–0.010	0.02	0.50
Hg ²⁺	c	0.50–1.01	3.20	0.40
Isonicotinic acid-hydrazide	c	0.10–0.23	2.80	0.44
Thiosemicarbazide	c	0.03–0.13	1.70	0.17
Thiourea	c	0.03–0.13	0.40	0.09
Phenol	c	0.01–0.20	1.70	0.40
Aniline	c	0.01–0.14	2.30	0.40

a Direct starch indicator, b Direct potentiometric, c Back titration, * Ten replicates.

The results show that all the titrations are very accurate and precise. In the potentiometric titrations of all but tin(II), sulphite and ascorbic acid, addition of 5 ml of saturated mercuric chloride solution is essential for the success of the titrations. So is the case with the direct visual titrations of the four reductants studied. The function of mercuric chloride in these cases is probably to remove the